

Dark and Bright Envelopes for Dehazing Images

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Abstract : We present a method for de-hazing images. A dark envelope image is derived with the bilateral minimum filter and a bright envelope is derived with the bilateral maximum filter. The ambient light and transmission of the scene are estimated from these two envelope images. An image without haze is reconstructed from the estimated ambient light and transmission.

Keywords : image dehazing, bilateral minimum filter, bilateral maximum filter, local contrast

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